

Pattern of cavities in globins: the case of human hemoglobin

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44 diffraction

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Abstract

In this paper we used the technique of filling with xenon atoms the hydrophobic cavities, previously referred to as packing defects, naturally present in myoglobin and hemoglobin. Our aim is to demonstrate up to which point the primary sequence is responsible for the globins' function; and to shed light on the conservation of potential ligand docking sites and on their role in protein dynamics. In particular, we present the high resolution structures of Xe-adduct of wild type sperm whale myoglobin and for the first time those of wild type human hemoglobin and of a quadruple mutant (L(B10)Y and H(E7)Q in both α and β chains), both in deoxy form. The analysis revealed that the number and position of cavities is different in Mb and in α and β subunits, suggesting a different dynamics for ligand migration within the protein matrix.

The number and position of hydrophobic cavities will be discussed also in view of the data available for other components of the globin superfamily.

Introduction

Cavities present within protein structures are not mere “packing defects” resulting from relaxed evolutionary pressure but play a role in dynamics and consequently in reaction mechanism¹. This picture is supported by cases where routes for substrate and product move to and from the active site can be mapped by the identification of cavities within the protein matrix².

One interesting, though not extreme, case is represented by the globin fold, where five to eight helices are arranged in a globular manner around a core, which hosts the heme group and consists of one long helix (E) closely hinged by a sharp corner to a short one (F). Despite the conservation among the regna and the common activity in gaseous ligands binding, there is a wide variation on the theme. Indeed this superfamily is formed by proteins whose roles span from catalysis to transport and storage of small ligands. This spectrum of activities is sustained by a wide sequence variability that allows tuning of affinity and reactivity and also by the presence of different cavity systems and tunnels that allow the access to the heme group and trapping of ligands within the protein matrix.

In sperm whale myoglobin (Mb) discrete cavities were identified that can transiently host CO during photodissociation³⁻⁶, in neuroglobin (Ngb) and cytoglobin (Cygb) a wide cavity that connects the heme to the bulk was identified^{7,8} and in Group I truncated hemoglobins (thHbs) a tunnel exists that connects directly the heme to the exterior⁹.

The network of cavities in globins has been investigated by different methods, allowing to characterize their tendency to host ligands and their dynamics. These approaches involve in crystals the use of xenon, that can dock into apolar niches⁸⁻¹⁰ and the direct determination of ligands trapped in the matrix after photodissociation^{3,5,11}. In solution spectroscopy coupled to kinetics can detect the presence of ligand docking intermediates^{12,13}. *In silico* molecular dynamics simulations can unveil the presence of transient cavities and describe the route of ligands within them^{14,15}.

The general picture conveyed by these studies for monomeric globins, is that cavities modulate ligand kinetics and therefore protein reactivity, on top of other structural determinants such as the hydrogen bonding potential of residues found in the distal heme site and the intrinsic heme reactivity^{16,17}.

In the case of tetrameric, cooperative hemoglobin (Hb) the situation is much more complex since, although ligand affinity is ultimately determined by the tertiary structure of each monomer, the quaternary T state of the tetramer induces restraints on binding that lower affinity. Despite the wealth of data from x-ray crystallography the precise stereochemical basis for the difference in oxygen affinity

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3 of the T and R states has not been understood, although it is clear that α and β chains show behaviours
4 which could underlie different regulation mechanisms¹⁸⁻²².

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7 The structure of the photolytic intermediates of CO bound T and R state human hemoglobin (HbA)
8 has shown that in the T state two docking sites can be observed for this ligand, one within the distal
9 heme site in both α and β chains and one corresponding to Mb Xe4 only for the β chains¹¹.

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12 Molecular dynamics and modelling studies have been carried out on the structure of HbA in order to
13 identify static and transient cavities within Hb chains^{23,24}. In both cases, despite their sequence
14 similarity and phylogenetic proximity, relevant differences have been pointed out in the pattern of
15 cavities displayed by the two types of chains.
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20 The question arises as to whether the pattern of internal cavities of HbA α and β chains might be
21 one of the factors determining the different behaviour displayed within the frame of the HbA tetramer,
22 especially in the T state. Under this respect the HbA mutants at topological position B10 and E7, i.e.,
23 Leu(B10)→Tyr and His(E7)→Gln, on either the α or the β chains alone, or on both types of chains
24 (HbYQ) are particularly interesting. The mutations on both chains lead to proteins with low affinity for
25 O₂ and CO, and to reduced reactivity toward NO^{25,26}. The observed kinetic heterogeneity between the
26 α YQ and β YQ chains in HbYQ has been rationalized on the basis of the three-dimensional structure of
27 the active site that could affect ligand diffusion into the pocket. In HbYQ, β chains seem to display
28 enhanced reactivity towards ligands with respect to α chains, in contrast with what observed in wt
29 HbA²⁶. The same mutations, introduced in sperm whale myoglobin (MbYQR) affected ligand kinetics
30 and affinity, a finding that was in part accounted for due to the variation in volume and accessibility of
31 Mb internal cavities²⁷.
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36 In order to describe the presence and accessibility of HbA chains cavities we have determined the
37 structure of deoxy high salt T-state HbA and HbYQ after exposure of the crystals to xenon. Indeed the
38 two types of chains display a significant difference under this respect, introducing a structural feature
39 for understanding regulation of Hb tetramer functionality, previously not taken into account.
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44 A comparison between the internal cavities mapped by xenon in HbA with sites determined with the
45 same approach in Mb and Cygb could shed light on their eventual conservation and correlation with
46 function, adding to the picture of how nature has achieved the task of performing different functions by
47 exploring a limited set of conformations and three dimensional structures.
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52 Family folds are very well conserved, but within each family the number of functions explored or
53 performed is wider than expected. Sometimes it is just a question of tuning, sometimes the reactions
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3 performed are completely different. It has been established that the sequence identity required to keep
4 the frame (or to maintain the fold) is as low as 16%, but once the frame is kept, almost everything can
5 change for a certain purpose²⁸: are protein cavities a conserved feature and how do they correlate with
6 protein function and dynamics?
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10 11 **Results**

12 *Xenon derivatives of myoglobin*

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14 Oxidised wild type sperm whale myoglobin (swMb) in complex with pressurised Xe had already
15 been solved¹⁰, but in this experiment we aimed at having the same protocol run for all the proteins in
16 order to better compare all results. Moreover in our case swMb is recombinant and crystallized in a
17 different space group from the wild type, therefore we could estimate to what extent docking of Xenon
18 into swMb is affected by these factors.
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24 As can be seen in Figure 1, swMb hosts 4 Xe atoms in the same positions already described by
25 Tilton and co-workers¹⁰. We decided to keep the same nomenclature for reference: hence Xe1 is the
26 site in the proximal part of the pocket near His 93 (the proximal Histidine in topological position F8);
27 Xe2 is lying almost in the plane of the heme next to one of the vinyl groups separating/linking the
28 proximal from the distal site; Xe3 is off the heme binding site and close to Xe2; and finally Xe4 is on
29 the distal part of the heme pocket behind Leu 29 (topological position B10).
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35 *Xenon derivatives of hemoglobins*

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37 A different scenario is offered by HbA and its mutant. First of all the α and β chains do not behave
38 similarly, confirming the functional heterogeneity reported in the literature [see ²⁹ for review].
39 Moreover, not only are the two chains different from each other, but they are also differ from Mb, the
40 most important difference being the absence of any proximal docking site.
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44 **HbA.** Analysis of the deoxy T HbA xenon adduct allowed the identification of 12 Xenon atoms per
45 tetramer, with different occupancies (Table I). Four Xe are located in $\alpha 1$, three in $\alpha 2$, and two in each β
46 chain. To these eleven atoms an extra one adds up docked at the surface of the $\beta 2$ subunit and in
47 contact with the solvent; hence we decided not to label it. In five positions it was necessary to model
48 double occupancies for the Xe atoms, accounting for two mutually exclusive docking sites, given the
49 presence of elongated density that do not correspond to the size of a single Xe atom.
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55 The overall structure of HbA is not significantly affected by xenon binding, the r.m.s.d. values
56 calculated for comparison with respect to the deposited structure (1A3N³⁰) is 0.24 Å on 141 main chain
57 atoms.
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3 Tables II and III list the amino acids that constitute the walls of each Xe docking niche. Whenever
4 the value for occupancies was lower than 0.2, a value corresponding to the electron content of a water
5 molecule, we assigned and refined a Xe atom only if: i) the position was not occupied by a water in the
6 structure determined in the absence of xenon; ii) the environment was hydrophobic, i.e. no hydrogen
7 bond could be assigned for the anchoring of a water molecule; iii) the distances from the Xe atom and
8 the surrounding atom were consistent with sum of van der Waals radii.
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14 **α chains.** Three Xe atoms (Xe1, Xe2, Xe3) are found within each α chain, they are all located on
15 the region of the protein that is distal with respect to the heme (Figure 1a).
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17 Xe1 is located among helix A, helix E and helix H, surrounded by hydrophobic side chains. This site
18 is clearly internal to the protein, but not shielded from the solvent by other chains forming the tetramer.
19 Docking of Xe1 does not induce a significant repositioning of side chains, with the exception of Trp14,
20 which shows in $\alpha 1$ an alternate position by rotating around the C α -C β bond, absent in the T structure
21 determined in the absence of xenon.
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23 Xe2 is found between helices B, E and G, it is close to Xe1 (6.46-5.94 Å, respectively for Xe2a and
24 Xe2b), the connection between these two sites seems to be gated by Trp14, and indeed the occupation
25 of the Xe2b alternative site in $\alpha 1$ is only compatible with its novel, least occupied (0.2) conformer.
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27 The site hosting Xe3, compatible with two very close Xe in $\alpha 1$ and only one in $\alpha 2$, is found in a
28 position that is not equivalent to any of the Mb Xe position, and it is between helix E and the CE
29 joining segment. It is lined, among others, by the conserved distal His58 C β atom. This site is the
30 closest to the heme iron (8.96 Å) and it is separated from the exterior only by His58 and by Phe46. In
31 $\alpha 1$ Phe46 shows a modest displacement from the position observed in the absence of xenon, that
32 propagates to the CE segment (with a C α of His45 displaced by 0.7 Å). This docking site is the closest
33 to the bulk, being separated from the exterior only by the CE amino acid stretch.
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35 A fourth xenon atom was found in $\alpha 1$ with low occupancy (0.2) located in a hydrophobic niche
36 between the CD loop and helix A, though very close to the solvent. It was retained since it corresponds
37 to Xe6 found in HbYQ and for consistency it was labelled Xe6.
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50 **β chains.** The first xenon of the β chains (Xe1) has the highest occupancy (0.9) and it is accounted
51 for by two alternate positions separated by 0.71 Å (Figure 1b). In the structure determined in the
52 absence of xenon, this site is occupied by a water molecule that is displaced by Xe1. It is positioned
53 between helix G, helix H and the heme, being in contact with one of the vinyl groups of the heme. This
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3 position is superimposable to one of Mb Xe atoms: in fact it corresponds to Xe2 (1.87-1.18 Å distance,
4 respectively, of the two alternate positions after superposition).
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7 Xe2 atom is located on the distal side of the heme group, between helix B and helix E, in a position
8 very close to Mb Xe4 (distance 1 Å). Its docking does not involve a significant displacement of the
9 surrounding side chains. This site is clearly internal to the protein, and not shielded from the solvent by
10 other chains forming the tetramer.
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14 **HbYQ.** Analysis of the xenon adduct of this quadruple mutant in the deoxy T state has been carried
15 out in comparison with the same structure determined in the absence of xenon (1Q18²⁵) and with that
16 of the above described HbA-Xe. We cannot exclude that some different structural features can be due
17 to its quasi-atomic resolution (1.07 Å) that might have highlighted details not detectable at lower
18 resolution (1.7 Å). Within the limits of this *caveat*, we believe that the detail at which xenon atoms and
19 protein conformation can be determined at this resolution makes a description of this structure useful
20 for the analysis of internal cavities in Hb.
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24 In order to facilitate the comparison, we decided to use the same coding for identifying xenon atoms
25 in HbYQ-Xe with respect to HbA-Xe. In the mutant tetramer we detected 15 xenon atoms: the same
26 found in HbA plus two extra sites in the α chains, with noticeable differences with respect to the wt
27 protein (Table I and Figure 2a).
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31 **α YQ chains.** Xe1 position is present in double conformation in both α chains, with a slightly higher
32 occupancy in α 2 than in the α 1 chain, depending on a less mobile Trp14, that in α 1 shows two
33 conformers, one of which is too close to Xe. The flexibility of this Trp14 is also evident in HbA,
34 though in α 1 only. Hence this is an indication of very good reproducibility of structural features
35 between HbA and HbYQ, in regions far from the mutated residues, despite the difference in resolution.
36 After superposition of HbA on HbYQ, Xe1 is only slightly displaced.
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40 Xe2 in the mutant α 1 chain is found in a position that corresponds closely to what observed in HbA,
41 although with an occupation of one of the alternative sites (Xe2b) which is at the limit of detection
42 (0.1). The prevention of docking is due to the presence of a different conformer of Leu105 from HbA.
43 The new conformer rotates around its C α -C β bond. This effect is more enhanced in α 2 where only the
44 Leu105 rotamer unfavourable to Xe2 docking is populated, hence marking its absence.
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48 The position of the Xe3 atom is the same as in HbA, i.e. between helix E and the CE joining
49 segment; nevertheless its occupancy is very low (0.15 in α 1 and 0.3 in α 2) and it was unequivocally
50 assigned only after comparison with HbA. This difference is mainly due to the fact that its docking site
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3 is formed by the distal His58, which in HbYQ is mutated to Gln. Moreover this substitution has the
4 effect of slightly repositioning the neighbouring CD junction, leading to an increased mobility of
5 Phe46, responsible in the α chains of gating the access of Xe3 from the solvent into its docking cavity.
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9 The atoms Xe4 and Xe5, are absent in HbA-Xe were no electron density was detected that could
10 hint the presence of even very low occupancy sites. This difference clearly arises from the two
11 rotamers adopted by Leu105 side chain: in $\alpha 1$ -YQ it adopts two conformation, one of which allows
12 Xe4 docking; in $\alpha 2$ -YQ only this favourable conformer is present. On the other hand, in HbA the
13 rotamer of Leu105 is filling in the cavity, making it not compatible with Xe4 and Xe5 docking.
14 Moreover Xe4 is in a position that corresponds topologically to Xe2 in β chains and to Xe4 in Mb,
15 (distance 2.59 Å), though slightly displaced towards helix G. It is positioned on top of the heme distal
16 side between helix B and E, and is in contact with Tyr29, that in HbA is a Leu. We believe that this is
17 another factor contributing to the creation of this extra docking, since the bulky Tyr side chain forms
18 one of the “walls” of the cavity.
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27 The docking site of Xe5 into the α chains is surrounded by helix E, G and H and it is determined by
28 the position of Leu105. Its position corresponds to Xe1 of β chains and Mb Xe2.
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31 Finally, the presence of the last xenon (Xe6) is clearly indicated in the $\alpha 2$ chain by the presence of a
32 distinct peak of electron density localized in a hydrophobic niche, not occupied by solvent in either
33 HbYQ or HbA in the absence of xenon. Nevertheless its refinement posed some difficulties leaving
34 some little residual positive and negative density surrounding the resulting difference map. This atom is
35 positioned between the CD loop and the A helix, in a cavity that is shielded from the solvent by
36 Leu113. This residue, being on the protein surface, is mobile and probably determines the low
37 occupancy of the corresponding Xe6 on $\alpha 1$ of HbA. No Xe was detected in a similar topology in Mb.
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43 **β YQ chains.** Xe1 is found in the same position as in the wild type, with a total occupancy of 1.0. Its
44 density is elongated and three alternate positions were refined for this atom. The refinement is not fully
45 satisfactory, yielding a "tube" of density centered in front of the vinyl group of the heme B-ring. This
46 feature indicates the presence of a hydrophobic channel that can host a Xe with more than one precise
47 position. The electron density is elongated towards the heme distal side and points towards the position
48 occupied by Xe1 in HbA β chains, and by Xe2 in Mb.
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54 Xe2 is barely detectable on both β chains, probably due to mutation Leu28→Tyr, and its placing
55 was confirmed only after superposition with HbA. As in that case, it corresponds to Xe4 of Mb.
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Discussion

Comparison of HbA with Mb-Xe

In Mb the correlation between the presence and kinetic availability to ligands of sites identified by xenon docking has been established with a wealth of kinetic, spectroscopic and structural data unparalleled for other systems^{3-6,31,32}. The first structural evidence leading to subsequent experimental and computational analysis was the identification of four xenon binding sites by protein crystallography¹⁰ that are located in the proximal region of Mb (Xe1), coplanar with respect to the heme (Xe2 and Xe3) and on top of the distal heme cavity (Xe4). Firm evidence exists that after photodissociation CO is first located in the distal pocket, then into Xe4 and subsequently into the proximal Xe1 cavity^{3-6,31-33}. Migration occurs probably through gating movements of Leu104 in and Ile107 in Mb that govern hopping of gaseous ligands from and to different sites^{27,32}.

We have carried out a comparison between deoxy T state HbA and Mb Xe sites that indicates the absence of proximal docking on α and β chains, consistent with the presence of several mutations in HbA proximal region to fill in the corresponding cavity occupied by Xe1 in Mb²⁹.

As shown in Figure 1a, there is no correspondence between Xe sites in HbA α chains and Mb. Four Xe binding cavities have been detected, with a topology new with respect to Mb. Two of them are internally docked: Xe1 trapped between helices A, E and H and Xe2 between helices B, E and G. Xe3 and Xe6 (only in $\alpha 1$) are slightly peripheral, but not external, and are respectively shielded by helix E and the CE junction, and by helix A and the CD loop.

On the other hand both HbA β chain sites are conserved in Mb: Xe1 matches Mb Xe2 (distance 1 Å) and Xe2 superimposes to Mb Xe4 (distance 1.04 Å).

The presence of a niche capable to host a Xe atom in both HbA β chains corresponding to Xe4 is in agreement with the finding by Adachi et. al¹¹ that, upon continuous photolysis at 25K of T state Hb-CO, CO is found in a site equivalent to Mb Xe4 only in the β chains.

HbYQ-Xe comparison with HbA-Xe and Mb-Xe.

We have determined the structure of deoxy T-state HbYQ-Xe carrying mutations Leu(B10)→Tyr and His(E7)→Gln on both α and β chains, prompted by the facts i) that the same mutations affected ligand occupation and dynamics in Mb and ii) that the behaviour of HbYQ is profoundly affected, with a marked decrease of α chains affinity, but still retaining cooperativity in the tetramer.

Indeed HbYQ-Xe β chains show no novel sites with respect to HbA, but a change was noticeable with respect to the wt. The tube of density hosting Xe1, elongates towards Xe2 showing an additional

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3 alternate Xe position. Xe2 decreases its occupancy with respect to wt. This is most likely due to the
4 mutation of Leu(B10)→Tyr. This side chain is one of the contacts of Xe2 atom and divides in two
5 compartments a niche that extends from the heme rim (vinyl group of heme ring B), where Xe1 is
6 hosted, up to the top of the heme (see Figure 2b). In both HbA and HbYQ the β chains closely
7 resemble Mb (Figure 1b and 1d), except for the absence of the proximal Mb Xe1. Mutations introduced
8 in HbYQ do not disrupt nor create new cavities, but rather affect their relative affinity for Xe and
9 possibly other gaseous ligands.
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16 The effect on α chains deserves a detailed discussion, since in one of them ($\alpha 2$) the Xe2 site is
17 absent, whereas in $\alpha 1$ it is retained (Figure 2a). Moreover two new Xe atoms appear in both α chains,
18 Xe4 and Xe5, that are close to Mb Xe4 (2.8 Å distance) and to Mb Xe2 (3.8 Å distance), respectively.
19 It is apparent that the position of Xe2 correlates with Leu105 conformer found in HbA whereas Xe4
20 and Xe5 can dock in the α chains only if the new conformer is populated. The formation of a docking
21 niche for Xe4 and Xe5, stabilized by the new conformer of Leu105, is due to the mutation
22 Leu(B10)→Tyr. This residue protrudes into the distal cavity and likely affects the conformation of
23 Leu105 nearby.
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31 The sites occupied by Xe1, Xe2 and Xe6 define a path from the bulk leading to the heme distal side.
32 The tyrosine introduced in position B10 blocks the access to the distal cavity and traps two additional
33 xenon atoms: Xe4 and Xe5. Therefore there seem to be two paths defined by Xe in Hb α chains: a
34 more direct one, from Xe3 to the heme; and a long tunnel, from Xe6 to Xe1 and Xe2 and finally Xe4
35 and Xe5 (the last two evident only in HbYQ). For both routes Tyr introduced in B10 acts like a septum,
36 interrupting the way from the bulk to the heme iron (Figure 2a). This is consistent with the fact that in
37 HbYQ the affinity of the α chains is lowered and if crystals of deoxy HbYQ are exposed to CO only
38 the β chains bind it, allowing the determination of the mixed α -unbound β -CO structure²⁶.
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46 In agreement with our data, molecular modelling study of T state HbA showed that a very wide
47 cavity opens only in the α chains, having three branches connected with the protein surface²³. By
48 comparing the list of 34 residues that line this transient cavity we found that 24 coincide with residues
49 lining the Xe cavities of the α chains in HbA and HbYQ.
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52 *Comparison with Xe sites in Cytoglobin.*

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Cytoglobin (Cyg**b**) is an intracellular hexacoordinated globin expressed in vertebrates, probably
endowed with catalytic function. Cyg**b** shows poor (15%) sequence conservation with respect to Mb
and has a large (240Å²) internal cavity, where four Xe docking sites have been identified by

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3 crystallography⁸. All those sites are distally located with respect to the heme, with some topological
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5 correspondence only between Cygb Xe1 and Mb Xe4. On the other hand there is very good correlation
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7 between Xe sites in Cygb and Hb α chains: i) HbA Xe1 is very close to Cygb Xe3 (1.84 Å); ii) HbA
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9 Xe2 is almost superimposable to Cygb Xe4 (1.39 Å); iii) Xe4 in α and Xe2 in β chains are in the same
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11 area of Cygb Xe1 (Figure 3).

12 13 14 **Conclusions**

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16 The analysis of the structures of deoxy HbA and deoxy HbYQ, in complex with Xe allowed to
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18 highlight a clear difference in the pattern of cavities and potential ligand routes within the α and β
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20 chains. In the β chains of both HbA and HbYQ only two Xe docking sites could be detected only
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22 slightly affected by the mutations Leu(B10)→Tyr and His(E7)→Gln, despite being located in the distal
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24 area. Both cavities in the β chains are close to the heme, and do not indicate routes of access or exit
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26 with respect of the heme distal binding site.

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28 In both proteins α chains a constellation of sites hosting up to 6 xenon atoms was detected, mapping
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30 the presence of cavities that describe potential paths from the bulk to the heme iron. In HbYQ these
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32 paths are interrupted by the tyrosine introduced in position B10. Hence we attribute the decreased
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34 propensity of this mutant to bind gaseous ligands to this reason.

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36 Our result is in agreement with previous experimental studies¹¹, since we have identified a docking
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38 site for photolyzed CO in the β chains (coincident with Xe2, corresponding to Mb Xe4) and we have
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40 experimentally confirmed the presence, only in the α chains, of a large dynamic cavity shown by
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42 molecular dynamics simulations²³.

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44 Concerning the conservation of Xe sites in globins, as an indicator of the presence of similar internal
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46 ligand tunnels and binding sites, it is evident that proximal cavities are absent in HbA and Cygb. This
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48 seems to indicate that only Mb is endowed with an apolar niche on the proximal side of the heme.

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50 It seems that β chains are more similar to Mb, since they share two sites (Xe1 and Xe2
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52 corresponding to Mb Xe2 and Xe4). Comparing HbA xenon binding sites with those of Cygb it seems
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54 that, despite a large phylogenetic distance between these two proteins and of the presence in Cygb of a
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56 large internal cavity, absent in the α chains, the positions mapped by xenon binding are very similar.
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58 Altogether it seems that the position corresponding to the distal Xe4 in Mb is the only one conserved in
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60 Mb, HbA chains and Cygb.

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3 Our data add another piece of information for explaining ligand affinity in HbA and the
4 heterogeneous behaviour of α and β chains, despite their evolutionary and structural similarity; their
5 heterogeneity could partially reside in the difference in the pattern of internal cavities. On the
6 speculative side we can conclude that the fine tuning of a given activity may be achieved by a small
7 number of mutations (as in HbA vs HbYQ), but in order to change register nature needs to change a
8 whole lot of amino acids, filling in cavities in a place and opening others in a different one. The
9 apparently rigid compactness of helices in the globin superfamily revealed to be a flexible framework
10 for nature to play with.
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20 **Materials and methods**

21 Recombinant wild type swMb was cloned into pUC91 vector, expressed into *Escherichia coli* TB-1
22 strain and purified as previously described³⁴.
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24 Human hemoglobin (HbA) was purified from red blood cells, and recombinant mutant HbYQ was
25 cloned into pKK223-3, expressed in *E. coli* TB-1 strain and purified as previously described²⁵.
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28 Oxidized swMb was concentrated to 20mg/ml in 20 mM Tris/HCl pH 8.7 and 1 mM EDTA and
29 crystallized by vapour diffusion at room temperature in hanging drops, using 2.7 M ammonium sulfate
30 – buffered with 0.1M Tris/HCl pH8.7 as precipitant.
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33 Deoxygenated HbA and HbYQ were concentrated to 60mg/ml in 20mM Na/K phosphate buffer pH
34 6.7 and crystallized at room temperature in batch using high salt conditions³⁵ under N₂. All the crystals
35 were mounted on a loop after being cryoprotected with 20% glycerol, except HbYQ for which 15%
36 trehalose was used.
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40 Pressurized Xenon was soaked into already-mounted crystals using the Oxford Cryosystem Xcell
41 apparatus; a high pressure flux of 10 atm for 1min. was used in each case. All the crystals were flash
42 frozen in liquid N₂ and stored until collected at 100K.
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46 Data collection of swMb was performed at ELETTRA (Trieste, I), HbYQ-Xe was collected at
47 DESY (Hamburg, G) and HbA-Xe was collected at ESRF (Grenoble, F).
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49 All the structures were indexed with Mosflm³⁶, and solved with programs from the CCP4 suite³⁷:
50 namely, they were scaled with SCALA³⁸, solved with MolRep³⁹, refined with Refmac5⁴⁰ and validated
51 with Procheck⁴¹. Model building was performed with Coot⁴² and figures were prepared with Pymol
52 (www.PyMOL.org).
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56 Given the high resolution of the three structures (1.9Å for SwMb, 1.8Å for HbA and 1.07 for
57 HbYQ) the occupancies of the Xe atoms were refined with good precision until their associated B-
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3 factors were in the range of the surrounding residues and there were no residuals in the Fo-Fc
4 difference maps. Moreover anisotropic refinement has been performed for HbYQ. The refinement
5 matrices used for the structures were the following: 0.3 for SwMb, 0.5 for HbA, and 3.0 for HbYQ.
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9 A summary of data collection and refinement statistics is presented in Table IV.

10 The coordinates and structure factors of all proteins have been deposited in the PDB using the EBI
11 Autodep facility; the codes assigned to the Xe-derivatives of the proteins presented in this paper are the
12 following: 2W6W to SwMb-Xe, 2W6V to HbA-Xe, and 2W72 to HbYQ-Xe.
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10 **Figures legends.**

11 Figure 1. Comparison between Hb and Mb. Ribbon representation of the xenon adduct of HbA and
12 HbYQ with swMb. Xe are represented in spheres, heme groups in sticks. Xe sites of Hb are labelled in
13 red, those of Mb in black.
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17 Panel a. HbA α chains (purple) superimposed to Mb (green).

18 Panel b. HbA β chains (blue) superimposed to Mb (green).

19 Panel c. HbYQ α chains (red) superimposed to Mb (green).

20 Panel d. HbYQ β chains (light blue) superimposed to Mb (green).
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27 Figure 2. Comparison between HbA and HbYQ.

28 Panel a. HbA α chains (purple) superimposed to HbYQ α chains (red).

29 Panel b. HbA β chains (dark blue) superimposed to HbYQ β chains (light blue).
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34 Figure 3. Comparison between HbYQ α chains (red) and Cygb (yellow). Xe sites for HbYQ are
35 labelled in blue and those for Cygb in black.
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Figure 1. Comparison between Hb and Mb. Ribbon representation of the xenon adduct of HbA and HbYQ with swMb. Xe are represented in spheres, heme groups in sticks. Xe sites of Hb are labelled in red, those of Mb in black. Panel a. HbA alpha chains (purple) superimposed to Mb (green). Panel b. HbA beta chains (blue) superimposed to Mb (green). Panel c. HbYQ alpha chains (red) superimposed to Mb (green). Panel d. HbYQ beta chains (light blue) superimposed to Mb (green).
194x181mm (600 x 600 DPI)

Comparison between HbA and HbYQ. Panel a. HbA alpha chains (purple) superimposed to HbYQ alpha chains (red). Panel b. HbA beta chains (dark blue) superimposed to HbYQ beta chains (light blue).

96x161mm (600 x 600 DPI)

Comparison between HbYQ alpha chains (red) and Cygb (yellow). Xe sites for HbYQ are labelled in blue and those for Cygb in black.
92x80mm (600 x 600 DPI)

Table I. Xe atoms positions and occupancies in HbA, HbYQ and swMb.

Xenon	HbA				HbYQ				SwMb	
	α 1	α 2	β 1	β 2	α 1	α 2	β 1	β 2		
Xe1a	0.3	0.5			0.3	0.4			Xe1 (proximal pocket)	0.9
Xe1b					0.1	0.15				
Xe2a	0.2	0.2			0.25				Xe2 (vinyl group)	0.5
Xe2b	0.4	0.2			0.1					
Xe3a	0.3	0.5			0.15	0.25			Xe3 (exit tunnel)	0.4
Xe3b	0.2					0.1				
Xe4					0.15	0.2			Xe4 (distal pocket)	0.4
Xe5					0.15	0.2				
Xe6	0.2				0.15	0.9				
Xe1a			0.4	0.4			0.65	0.7		
Xe1b			0.5	0.5			0.1	0.15		
Xe1c							0.2	0.15		
Xe2			0.2	0.3			0.1	0.15		
Xe-Extra				0.5						

Table II. Amino acids forming the cavities hosting Xe in α subunits of HbA and HbYQ, as identified by having at least one atom at a distance within a cut-off of 4.5 Å from Xe. Mutations are highlighted in bold, when present.

	HbA α subunit	HbYQ α chain
		Val 10
	Trp 14	Trp 14
	Val 70	Val 70
Xe1	Leu 125	Leu 105
	Phe 128	Leu 109
	Leu 129	Leu 125
		Phe 128
		Leu 129
		Trp 14
	Trp 14	Ala 21
	Ala 21	Tyr 24
Xe2	Tyr 24	Gly 26
	Gly 25	Ala 63
	Thr 108	Leu 66
	Leu 109	Leu 105
		Leu 109
	Leu 29	
	Phe 33	Phe 33
Xe3	Phe 46	Phe 43
	Leu 48	Phe 46
	Val 55	Leu 48
	His 58	Val 55
		Gly 25
		Ala 28
Xe4		Tyr 29
		Val 62
		Leu 66
		Leu 105
		Leu 129
		Vinyl group of heme ring B
Xe5		Leu 66
		Leu 101
		Ser 102
		Leu 105
		Leu 129
	Ala 13	Ala 13
Xe6	Leu 113	Leu 109
	Glu 116	Leu 113
	Phe 117	Glu 116
	Ala 121	Phe 117
	Leu 125	Val 121
		Leu 125

Table III. Amino acids forming the cavities hosting Xe in β subunits of HbA and HbYQ, as identified by having at least one atom at a distance within a cut-off of 4.5 Å from Xe. Mutations are highlighted in bold, when present.

	HbA β chain	HbYQ β chain
	Vinyl group of heme ring B	Vinyl group of heme ring B
		Leu 68
		Phe 71
		Phe 103
Xe1	Gly 107	Gly 107
	Val 134	Leu 110
	Val 137	Val 134
		Val 137
		Ala 138
	Gly 24	Gly 24
	Leu 28	Ala 27
Xe2	Gly 64	Tyr 28
	Val 67	Gly 64
	Leu 68	Val 67
	Leu 106	Leu 68
	Ala 138	Leu 106

Table IV. Xray diffraction data and Refinement statistics.

PDB entry	Resolution (Å) ^a	SG and cell dimension	Completeness (%) ^a	Rsym ^{a,b}	$\langle I/\sigma \rangle$ ^{a,c}	r.m.s.d. bond length (Å)	r.m.s.d. bond angles (°)	Ramachandran distribution ^d	Rwork (%)	Rfree (%)
2W6W - swMb	1.9 (2.0-1.9)	P6; a=b=90.63; c= 45.5Å	99.6 (94.8)	0.045 (0.38)	15.6 (2.5)	0.01	0.88	99.6/0.4/0/0	18.7	20.5
2W6V - HbA	1.79 (1.84-1.79)	P2 ₁ ; a=62.64Å; b=82.33Å; c=53.55Å; β=99.8°	99.7 (96.4)	0.058 (0.25)	14.2 (2.3)	0.016	1.62	99.8 / 0.2 / 0 / 0	16.2	21.5
2W72 - HbYQ	1.07 (1.09-1.07)	P2 ₁ ; a=61.96Å; b=82.45Å; c=53.53Å; β=99.6°	94.2 (88.3)	0.034 (0.31)	18.2 (2.5)	0.016	1.81	99.8 / 0.2 / 0 / 0	12.9	15.3

^a The number between parenthesis is for the last resolution shell.

^b $R_{sym} = \sum |I - \langle I \rangle| / \sum I$, where I=observed intensity, $\langle I \rangle$ =average over Friedel and symmetry equivalents.

^c Represents an average of the ratio of the intensity over the evaluated error on intensity measurement.

^d Ratio of nonglycine:nonproline residues that fall within one of the following regions of the Ramachandran plot: most favored/ additional allowed/ generously allowed/ disallowed, as output by the program PROCHECK.